

Heuristic Proposal to Design and Assess Pervasiveness in Video Games

In order to characterize the pervasiveness of a digital game, the following set of heuristics are proposed:

Nº	SPATIAL DIMENSION HEURISTICS
SpD1	The game (or parts of it) has to be played in some physical scenario of real life
SpD2	The game blurs the boundaries of the game space (there is no clear separation between the game world and the real world)
SpD3	The player is aware of his/her position in the expanded game world (combination of real and virtual world)
SpD4	The player knows the position of other players in the expanded game world
SpD5	The player has to move to different locations in the real world, or between virtual locations representing real-world places, according to game requirements
SpD6	The game is able to reflect that the player has moved to a place in the real world
SpD7	The game includes challenges that use real objects present in the player's context
SpD8	The game can represent in the virtual scenarios of the game, real places that exist in the real life of the player
SpD9	The game allows to add virtual representations to real objects in the context of the player
SpD10	The game is able to spread through different localizations (real and virtual scenarios)
SpD11	The game can adapt the game scenarios to the player's own characteristics (e.g., modifying the game space or the appearance of characters and objects)
SpD12	The physical objects with which the player can interact in the game are naturally introduced (are well integrated) into the physical context of the player
SpD13	The digital elements of the game (audios, screening, virtual objects) are naturally integrated into the physical context of the player. If it is necessary, virtual objects are related to their physical counterparts
SpD14	The player is able to identify the objects of their physical context that are part of the game
SpD15	The player is able to identify objects from their physical context that have been introduced into the virtual world of the game
SpD16	The game is able to reflect that the player has made use of an object from its physical context which has an effect in the game (for example, using a musical keyboard connected with the game)
SpD17	The game is able to reflect that the player has made use of a virtual object introduced into their physical context (e.g., an augmented reality laser)
SpD18	The game encourages (through challenges) that the player knows places in their physical context or moves to them
SpD19	The game may alter the state of certain places or objects in the player's physical context (for example, by placing QRs that the player will then have to scan, or by asking the player to act on the real world)
SpD20	The game may modify its rules due to existing rules in the player's physical context
SpD21	Some factors present in physical play contexts may involve a certain level of insecurity (traffic, slopes, dangerous people, etc.). Therefore, the game takes into account risks in the users' context

Nº	SOCIAL DIMENSION HEURISTICS
SocD1	The game allows people from the player's social context to participate
SocD2	The game encourages player interaction (through challenges) with people in the player's context

SocD3	The game reflects what is happening in the user's social context and it adapts to changes in the state of the players social context
SocD4	The game is able to automatically adapt its challenges and/or dynamics when new players are integrated
SocD5	The player is aware of their own participation and that of other players in their social environment
SocD6	The game allows the player to create groups or teams with people (non-players and players) in their environment
SocD7	The game includes mechanisms to solve communication or collaboration problems between the player and the members of their team in the real world (e.g. leadership, resolving conflicts, ...)
SocD8	The game is able to adapt its challenges and/or group dynamics depending on the characteristics of the player (preferences, interaction, etc.) and their social context (player's interpersonal relationships, cultural environment, etc.)
SocD9	The game allows interaction of players in both the virtual and physical world, facilitating mixed interaction between players
SocD10	The game incorporates mechanisms that enable players to track their progress toward objectives while collaborating with a team from their social context
SocD11	The game encourages spontaneous social interactions
SocD12	The game has mechanisms for spontaneous intervention of people from the social context of the player
SocD13	Some people may participate in the game without being aware of it
SocD14	Some players may participate in the game and go unnoticed by other players
SocD15	The game allows to include virtual characters that represent people who exist in the player's social context
SocD16	The player is able to identify virtual players who represent people from their social context
SocD17	The game can have an impact on the social context of the player (create or intensify relationships with people in the environment, meet new people, etc.)

Nº	TEMPORAL DIMENSION HEURISTICS
TD1	There is no clear separation between when you are playing and when you are not because the game's activities integrate very well into real life
TD2	The game motivates the player to continue with the game beyond the game session (the concept of game session is fuzzy)
TD3	The game contains challenges that have no time limit
TD4	The game is able to modify the time limits of some challenges dynamically depending on the characteristics of the player
TD5	The game can be adapted taking into account the time constraints of the player and their context
TD6	Game worlds persist between game sessions
TD7	The game allows asynchronous communication between players so that communications occur more freely
TD8	There is uncertainty about when the game should be played (the game may be asleep for a while and require to be played at a certain time)
TD9	The game can be played at different temporal contexts (the game sessions can be distributed in different time periods)
TD10	The player has a continuous perception of the game, without loss of immersion throughout the changes between the virtual world and the real world
TD11	The game is able to offer different scenarios and interaction channels over time
TD12	The game influences the player's agenda in their daily lives
TD13	The game can keep running and making decisions even when no one is playing
TD14	The game may require the realization of challenges at inappropriate moments and generate some undesirable situation in the real world